

SIZING ASPECTS OF FLUID CONCRETE BEAMS REINFORCED WITH FIBERS

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ABSTRACT

The use of FRC for structural purposes has been gradually increasing and this growth has resulted in the emergence of standards such as the fib Model Code. This standard represents the calculation aspects for dimensioning FRC elements, however, the dimensioning steps are not fully illustrated. Thus, and to contribute to these steps, this work aims to determine an equation for the tensile stress of fibers for FRC beams. For this purpose, situations of sections reinforced with fibers and reinforcement (combined situation) and sections reinforced only with fibers were analyzed. Then, the values determined by the equation proposed in this work were compared with those stipulated in accordance with the fib Model Code. Thus, it was verified that for the combined situation, the values did not present significant discrepancies, however, for the section reinforced only with fibers, the variations were more discrepant, showing that the methodology proposed presents a conservative aspect. It is worth mentioning that, when using the equation proposed in this work, the tension value will present a conservative aspect and, although this work cannot be adapted to all situations of FRC structural elements, it is clear from the investigation that there may be an influence of the methodology used to obtain the tensile stress of the fibers, which demonstrates future perspectives for new work on the subject.

KEYWORDS: Fiber Reinforced Concrete, Tensile Stress of Fibers, Design Aspects, FRC Beams.

I. INTRODUCTION

The incorporation of fibers into concrete provides the composite with an increase in ductility and tenacity, improves control of the crack opening process, minimizes excessive cracking, increases impact resistance and, most importantly, promotes post-cracking concrete resistance, in which the fibers intercept the progression of the cracks, preventing sudden rupture of the fiber reinforced concrete element [1], [2].

In view of the above, the use of fiber reinforced concrete (FRC) has been gradually increasing worldwide and has undergone several advances over the last 15 years. With this advance, there are several applications of FRC in civil construction, such as its use in concrete floors and pavements, precast concrete and shotcrete. However, as studies advance, the applications of fiber reinforced concrete are also expanding, and FRC is being extensively studied in structural applications, such as the use of fiber reinforced concrete in beams and slabs [3], [4], [5].

This evolution in the use of FRC has been occurring because research on fiber reinforced concrete has begun to highlight the application of fibers as a structural material, based on the development of fracture mechanics concepts to describe the residual tensile strength of FRC due to the stress transfer bridge mechanism [1], [2], [6]. The development of these concepts should be based on the study of the residual strength provided by fiber reinforcement, in which, based on constitutive laws, crack openings in the tensile part of the concrete are observed.

Thus, through the constitutive relations for the dimensioning of fiber reinforced concrete structures, it is possible to develop the calculation aspects that must be considered to design a structural project produced with FRC elements [7], [8], [9]. It is worth noting that there are normative instructions in the literature that illustrate the calculation aspects to design a structural project produced with FRC

elements, such as the material described in the fib Model Code 2020 [10], in ACI 544.8R [11] and in NBR 16935 [12].

However, although these standards illustrate the calculation aspects that must be considered when dimensioning fiber reinforced concrete structural elements, they do not fully illustrate the dimensioning steps. In this sense, it is essential to conduct studies related to the dimensioning step of FRC structures to contribute to the understanding of the dimensioning steps and the possible checks that must be performed.

Furthermore, another important aspect to be taken into consideration when using FRC in structural applications concerns the use of a fiber reinforced fluid concrete. This is justified because fluid concrete, characterized by high fluidity, allows this fluidity to distribute the fibers more uniformly, making it possible to use the concrete casting flow to orient the fibers, allowing them to be concentrated in the locations and directions of greatest stress [13], [14], [15], [16].

In this context, authors such as Martinie and Roussel [13] analyzed the tensile strength of concretes that had preferentially oriented fibers and, through their studies, they realized that when the fibers were aligned with the tension lines, the reinforcement efficiency was 100%, while in the case of random dispersion of the fibers, the reinforcement efficiency was reduced to 30%. In view of this, the mechanical behavior of a concrete that presents a preferential orientation of the fibers, as is the case of a fluid concrete reinforced with fibers, may be different from the mechanical behavior of a concrete that presents randomly distributed fibers.

Based on this, and knowing that the aforementioned regulations do not verify the validity of the preferential orientation of the fibers and do not fully illustrate the FRC dimensioning steps, the present work aims to determine an equation regarding the tensile stress of fibers for steel fiber reinforced fluid concrete beams (SFRFC) and for polymer fiber reinforced fluid concrete beams (PFRFC). For this, situations of section reinforced with fibers and reinforcement (combined situation) and of section reinforced only with fibers were analyzed.

This article was divided into four sections. The first section is an introduction and contextualization of the topic and also shows the objective of the work. The second is the methodology used in the study, such as the presentation of the characterization and dosage of the materials and the application of the three-point bending test. The third is the results and discussions section, where the definition of the neutral axis positioning and an equation for the final tensile stress of the fibers are presented. And the fourth is the conclusion of the work, which also shows perspectives for future work.

II. METHODOLOGY

This section illustrates information on the material characterization and dosage used in the production of concrete, and represents the assembly of the three-point bending test used on the beams. It is worth mentioning that this work is a continuation of the work of Lima and Barboza [17], so similar information regarding the dosage and application of the test can be seen in both works. However, the approach of the work of Lima and Barboza [17] refers to the FRC loads and the approach of this work refers to an equation for the FRC.

2.1. Material Characterization and Dosage

Regarding the matrix of the concretes produced, the following materials were used: fine aggregate (sand), coarse aggregate (gravel), cement (CP V ARI RS), mineral addition (RBMG – Residue of Beneficiation of Marble and Granite), superplasticizer additive and water. Regarding the fibers used in the concretes, steel fibers were used for the SFRFC and polymeric fibers for the PFRFC, where the characteristics of these fibers are illustrated in Table 1. And regarding the reinforcements used for the combined situation, CA-50 steel bars with a diameter of 8 mm and 5.5 mm were used for the longitudinal and transverse reinforcement, respectively.

Table 1. Properties of steel fibers and polymer fibers, respectively.

Steel fibers		Polymeric fibers	
Parameter	Correspondence	Parameter	Correspondence
Format			
Classification	Type AI	Length (mm)	40
Form factor	80	Form factor	90
Density (g/cm ³)	7.85	Density (g/cm ³)	0.92
Longitudinal modulus of elasticity (GPa)	210	Longitudinal modulus of elasticity (GPa)	9.50
Tensile strength (MPa)	1100	Tensile strength (MPa)	600 – 650

Regarding the matrix dosage, an adaptation of the method by Gomes et al. [18] for fluid concrete was used, where the procedure was performed in three phases: obtaining the paste composition, determining the aggregate mixing ratio and selecting the paste content. And in relation to the fiber content, this parameter was determined using the concept of critical fiber volume proposed by Bentur and Mindess [19]. Thus, for the present work, a volumetric content of 0.4% was adopted for SFRFC and 1.0% for PFRFC. After that, the consumption of materials per m³ was defined for the two concretes produced (Table 2).

Table 2. Consumption of materials per m³.

Materials	Mass (kg)
Cement	377.90
RBMG	188.95
Fine aggregate	774.53
Coarse aggregate	813.75
Initial water	151.16
Complementary water	37.75
Absorption water	11.17
Superplasticizer	6.30
For the SFRFC	
Steel fibers	25.98 ($V_f = 0.4\%$)
For the PFRFC	
Polymeric fibers	3.78 ($V_f = 1.0\%$)

The concretes were produced according to the material consumption illustrated in Table 2, where 16 beams with 150 x 150 x 550 mm were produced, as recommended by EN 14651 [20], of which 8 were steel fiber reinforced fluid concrete (SFRFC) beams and 8 polymer fiber reinforced fluid concrete (PFRFC) beams. It is worth mentioning that the objective of this study was to produce a fluid concrete and, to verify this fluidity condition, the test performed was the spreading test.

According to NBR 15823-2 [21], for a concrete to be considered fluid, the spread of the mixture and the flow time of the concrete must be within the range of 650 to 850 mm and 3.0 to 7.0 seconds, respectively. For SFRFC, the spread and flow time corresponded to 700 mm and 4.0 seconds, respectively. And for PFRFC, the spread and flow time corresponded to 710 mm and 4.4 seconds, respectively. Thus, it was observed that the fluidity condition of the analyzed concretes was proven.

2.2. Application of the Three-Point Bending Test

To apply the three-point bending test, standardized by EN 14651 [20], the Shimadzu universal testing machine was used, where the test script was previously configured in the Trapezium X software. As an illustration, Figure 1 shows how the tests were performed.

Figure 1. Experiment setup.

From Figure 1, it is possible to observe the diagram that represents the experiment setup: (1) Shimadzu universal testing machine together with the test specimen and LVDTs positioned; (2) computer that presents the Trapezium X software; and (3) Spider 8 acquisition system together with the computer that presents the ITOM software. From this, the Trapezium X software provided data that related the test time with the applied load, while the ITOM software provided data that related the time with the crack opening.

In order to reconcile the two sets of data mentioned, a scan of the time values recorded by ITOM was performed, returning the associated load values in the spreadsheets provided by Trapezium X, which allowed relating the load parameters to the crack width recorded by the LVDTs. Thus, from the application of the bending test, it was possible to perform a graphical analysis of the results, where two curves are generated, one referring to force versus displacement and the other related to force versus test time (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Illustration of the results obtained by the test.

Through the curves illustrated in Figure 2, it is possible to obtain the load applied to the composite for certain displacements and that, from pre-established times, its associated loads are obtained. Furthermore, in parallel with the tests, photos were taken every 10 seconds regarding the progress of crack opening of the test specimens, with the aim of verifying the cracking time for each of the beams studied.

Therefore, the cracking time for each beam tested was verified through analysis of the images, starting from the verification of the first apparent crack. Thus, from the establishment of this time, the

cracking load was determined. Furthermore, the application of this test also provides data regarding the maximum load applied to the composite, which is the value corresponding to the highest load supported. With this, a comparative study can be made between the mentioned loads and this analysis is illustrated in the work of Lima and Barboza [22].

Subsequently, after the comparative analysis between the loads, this work determined the positioning of the neutral axis of the structure and, after that, from the equilibrium of the section and through the theory of bending in beams, an equation was defined regarding the tensile stress of fibers in the tensioned part of the concrete. To establish this parameter, as previously mentioned, situations of section reinforced with fibers and reinforcement (combined situation) and of section reinforced only with fibers were analyzed.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section presents the results regarding the definition the positioning of the neutral axis of the analyzed beams and the equation regarding the tensile stress of fibers in the tensioned part of the concrete, for situations of section reinforced with fibers and reinforcement and section reinforced only with fibers, respectively.

3.1. Definition the Neutral Axis Positioning

The positioning of the structure's neutral axis can be obtained by defining indicators a and c (Figure 3), where the first corresponds to the tensile height of the plastic response (longitudinal length of the first apparent crack) and the second is equivalent to the tensile height of the elastic response. To this end, the height corresponding to the first apparent crack was initially defined analytically for each of the beams analyzed, which represents the tensile height of the plastic response (Table 3), and a numerical validation study of this length was carried out.

Figure 3. Structural element analyzed [23].

Table 3. Height referring to the first crack for SFRFC and PFRFC beams, respectively.

SFRFC			PFRFC		
Beam	Height (px)	Height (mm)	Beam	Height (px)	Height (mm)
B1	656	42.50	B1	771	50.00
B2	769	49.80	B2	744	48.20
B3	808	52.40	B3	744	48.20
B4	823	53.30	B4	726	47.00
B5	780	50.50	B5	735	47.60
B6	702	45.50	B6	767	49.70
B7	810	52.50	B7	756	49.00
B8	764	49.50	B8	787	51.00

Average	49.50	Average	48.84
Standard deviation	3.74	Standard deviation	1.34

According to the data shown in Table 3 regarding the SFRFC, it is observed that the height of the first crack of the sample is equivalent to an average of 49.50 mm with a standard deviation of 3.74 mm (49.50 ± 3.74 mm). Regarding the PFRFC, it is verified that the height of the first crack of the sample is equivalent to an average of 48.84 mm with a standard deviation of 1.34 mm (48.84 ± 1.34 mm). In order to establish a value that represents both the beams with steel and polymeric fibers, the two specified intervals were used, in which the value referring to the height of the first crack corresponding to 50 mm was established.

With this definition, a validation study of this length was carried out numerically (using the ABAQUS software), in which the type of stress that the part was undergoing at this specific height was observed (Figure 4). Thus, it was found that from the stress evolution points along the crack as a function of the test time, all stress values were positive, which means that for the tensile height corresponding to 50 mm, tensile stress only occurs along the crack. In analyzing this, this behavior was already expected, since the height used for the study corresponds to the tensile height related to the plastic response and compressive stresses do not yet exist, which validates the behavior of the tensile height determined regarding the plastic response.

Figure 4. Representation of the tensile height corresponding to the plastic response.

Therefore, in order to determine the positioning of the structure's neutral axis, the same analysis was performed for other predetermined heights (62.5 mm, 75 mm, 87.5 mm, 100 mm, 112.5 mm and 125 mm), where the type of stress that the part was undergoing at these heights was observed. These heights were defined based on the traction length related to the plastic response and followed an increment pattern of 12.5 mm (corresponding to half the height of the notch made in the tested beams), and the results related to this study are illustrated in Table 4.

Table 4. Tension values at the edges referring to pre-established heights.

Centroid (mm)	Tensile	Compression	Variation (%)
62.5	Only tensile		–
75.0	0.013	0.013	0.0
87.5	0.014	0.007	+100.0
100.0	0.051	0.029	+75.9
112.5	0.019	0.036	- 47.2
125.0	Only compression		–

Analyzing the data in Table 4, it is observed that, in general, all stress values can be considered null, since these results tend to zero, and the largest number of decimal places was used to investigate the

variations between the tensile and compressive stresses at the edges referring to the pre-established heights. For the height corresponding to 62.5 mm, there is only a tensile stress request; for the height of 75 mm, the tensile stress was equivalent to the compressive stress; for the heights of 87.5 mm and 100 mm, the tensile stress was greater than the compressive stress by around 100% and 76%, respectively; for the height of 112.5 mm, the compressive stress was greater than the tensile stress by around 47%; and, for the height equivalent to 125 mm, there is only a compressive stress request.

Therefore, it is known that for the heights corresponding to 62.5 mm and 125 mm, the neutral axis is not positioned at these lengths, since at these edges there is a predominance of a single type of stress request, and this happens because both types of request must exist for the neutral axis of the structure to be considered, since it is in this position that the separation of the tensioned part from the compressed part of the element occurs. For the other heights investigated (75 mm, 87.5 mm, 100 mm and 112.5 mm), it is verified that there are both types of requests and that the limit height for this type of behavior to occur is 112.5 mm. Thus, to investigate the height corresponding to the depth of the neutral axis of the structure, the corresponding crack opening was verified for each of the heights that presented both types of requests.

From this, it was found that for centroid heights equivalent to 75 mm, 87.5 mm and 100 mm, the crack open (w_u) for all analyzed beams was measured at the serviceability limit state, since $1.5 \text{ mm} \leq w_u < 2.5 \text{ mm}$. Similarly, for the centroid height equivalent to 112.5 mm, the crack open for all analyzed beams was measured at the ultimate limit state, since $2.5 \text{ mm} \leq w_u < 3.5 \text{ mm}$. Therefore, it is found that the only crack open measured at the ultimate limit state was the one equivalent to the height of 112.5 mm and the other opens were measured at the serviceability limit state.

Thus, considering as a parameter the ultimate limit state of the element (crack open $w_u \geq 2.5 \text{ mm}$), it was found that the height of the centroid equivalent to 112.5 mm corresponds to the positioning of the neutral axis of the analyzed FRC structure. Therefore, it can be stated that the distance from the neutral axis to the most compressed part of the element and the distance from the neutral axis to the most tensioned part of the element is, respectively, $x = 37.5 \text{ mm}$ and $y = 112.5 \text{ mm}$.

3.2. Tensile Stress of Fibers – Section Reinforced with Fibers and Reinforcement

After establishing the positioning of the structure's neutral axis, for combined situations (fibers and reinforcement), the representation of the cross-section of the beam used in the bending test, the deformation diagram and the distribution of the FRC section resistances are illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Representation of the element cross-section, deformation diagram and resistance distribution (section reinforced with fibers and reinforcement).

Analyzing Figure 5, the representation of the FRC compression stress and the FRC tensile stress was made in relation to the force resulting from these requests, which are the resultant of the FRC normal compression stress (R_{cd}) and the resultant of the FRC normal tensile stress (R_{td}), respectively. To determine these forces, Equations 1 and 2 can be used as assistance. Furthermore, the resultant of the conventional reinforcement tensile force (R_{sd}) can be determined by means of Equation 3.

$$R_{cd} = \alpha_c \eta_c f_{cd} \cdot \lambda x \cdot b_w \tag{1}$$

$$R_{td} = f_{ftud} \cdot y \cdot b_w \quad (2)$$

$$R_{sd} = f_{yd} \cdot A_s \quad (3)$$

Continuing, a study was carried out regarding the determination of the tensile stress of fibers in the tensioned part of the FRC (f_{ftud}) and this analysis is shown below. For this investigation, the Euler-Bernoulli Theory for beams was applied and through the equilibrium of the section, the study regarding the determination of f_{ftud} . The equilibrium of the forces acting normal to the cross section was applied and then the equilibrium of the moments in relation to the geometric center of the reinforcement (Equations 4 and 5). Thus, it is possible to determine the tensile stress of fibers in the tensioned part of the concrete for combined situations of fibers and reinforcement (Equations 6 to 8).

- Equilibrium of the forces acting normal to the cross section:

$$\sum F_x = 0 \rightarrow$$

$$R_{sd} + R_{td} - R_{cd} = 0 \quad (4)$$

- Equilibrium of the moments in relation to the geometric center of the reinforcement:

$$\sum M_{A_s} = 0 \curvearrowright$$

$$-R_{td} \left(\frac{y}{2} - i \right) + R_{cd} \left(y - i + \left(\frac{\lambda x}{2} \right) \right) - M_{rd} = 0 \quad (5)$$

- Tensile stress of fibers in the tensioned part of the concrete:

Combining Equations 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5, we have:

$$f_{ftud} = \frac{f_{yd} A_s (-\lambda x + 2i - 2y) + 2M_{rd}}{b_w y (\lambda x + y)} \quad (6)$$

Where $\rightarrow f_{ftud}$: tensile stress of fibers in the tensioned part of the concrete (kPa); f_{yd} : yield stress of the steel (MPa); M_{rd} : design bending moment resistance (kN.m) – Equations 7 and 8; A_s : steel area of the longitudinal reinforcement (m²); x : distance from the neutral axis of the structure to the most compressed part of the element (m); y : distance from the neutral axis of the structure to the most tensioned part of the element (m); b_w : base of the cross-section (m); i : difference between the height and the useful height of the element (m).

$$M_{sd} = \left((\alpha_c \eta_c f_{cd} \cdot \lambda x \cdot b_w) \cdot \left(\frac{y + \lambda x}{2} \right) \right) + \left((f_{yd} \cdot A_s) \cdot \left(d - \lambda x - \frac{y}{2} \right) \right) \quad (7)$$

$$M_{rd} = 1,4M_{sd} \quad (8)$$

In order to verify the Equation proposed in this work (Equation 6), this equation was compared with the Equations determined in accordance with the fib model code 2020 [10]. For this, the same parameters required for the equations were adopted and the results found are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Tensile stress of fibers (section reinforced with fibers and reinforcement).

SFRFC		
Analysis parameter	Tensile stress (MPa)	Variation (%)
Analytical study	3.03	-
fib model code 2020 [10]	2.64	+12.85
PFRFC		
Analysis parameter	Tensile stress (MPa)	Variation (%)
Analytical study	2.18	-
fib model code 2020 [10]	1.91	+12.52

Analyzing the data in Table 5, it can be seen that, when comparing the tensile stress of the SFRFC obtained by the analytical study with that determined in accordance with the fib model code 2020, the value by the first method is greater than the second by around 12%. In parallel, when comparing the tensile stress of the PFRFC obtained by the analytical study with that determined in accordance with the fib model code 2020, the value by the first is also greater than the second by around 12%. This shows that when comparing the two methods used, the value established from the equation illustrated in this work is greater than that determined from the fib equation.

3.3. Tensile Stress of Fibers – Section Reinforced Only with Fibers

After establishing the positioning of the structure's neutral axis, for situations of sections reinforced only with fibers, the representation of the cross-section of the beam used in the bending test, the deformation diagram and the distribution of the CRF section resistances are illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Representation of the element cross-section, deformation diagram and resistance distribution (section reinforced only with fibers).

Analyzing the Figure 6, it is possible to determine the tensile stress of fibers in the tensioned part of the concrete. To do this, the equilibrium of the forces acting normal to the cross section was also applied and then the equilibrium of the moments in relation to point C (Equations 9 and 10).

- Equilibrium of the forces acting normal to the cross section:

$$\sum F_x = 0 \rightarrow$$

$$R_{rd} - R_{cd} = 0 \tag{9}$$

- Equilibrium of moments in relation to point C:

$$\sum M_C = 0 \curvearrowright$$

$$-R_{rd} \left(\frac{y}{2}\right) + R_{cd} \left(y + \frac{\lambda x}{2}\right) - M_{rd} = 0 \tag{10}$$

- Tensile stress of fibers in the tensioned part of the concrete:

Combining Equations 1, 2, 9 and 10, we have:

$$f_{Ftud} = \frac{2M_{rd}}{b_w y (\lambda x + y)} \quad (11)$$

Where $\rightarrow f_{Ftud}$: tensile stress of fibers in the tensioned part of the concrete (kPa); M_{rd} : design bending moment resistance (kN.m) – Equations 8 and 12; x : distance from the neutral axis of the structure to the most compressed part of the element (m); y : distance from the neutral axis of the structure to the most tensioned part of the element (m); b_w : base of the cross-section (m).

$$M_{sd} = (\alpha_c \eta_c f_{cd} \cdot \lambda x \cdot b_w) \cdot \left(\frac{y + \lambda x}{2} \right) \quad (12)$$

Similar to the previous analysis, and with the aim of verifying the equation proposed in this work (Equation 11), this equation was also compared with the Equations determined in accordance with the fib model code 2020 [10], as can be seen in Table 6.

Table 6. Tensile stress of fibers (section reinforced only with fibers).

SFRFC		
Analysis parameter	Tensile stress (MPa)	Variation (%)
Analytical study	2.25	-
fib model code 2020 [10]	1.67	+25.78
PFRFC		
Analysis parameter	Tensile stress (MPa)	Variation (%)
Analytical study	2.10	-
fib model code 2020 [10]	1.43	+31.90

Observing the Table 6, it can be seen that, when comparing the tensile stress of the SFRFC obtained by the analytical study with that determined in accordance with the fib model code 2020, the value by the first method is greater than the second by around 25%. In parallel, when comparing the tensile stress of the PFRFC obtained by the analytical study with that determined in accordance with the fib model code 2020, the value by the first is also greater than the second by around 31%. This shows that when comparing the two methods used, the value established from the equation illustrated in this work is greater than that determined from the fib equation.

Therefore, it can be seen that the result defined by the fib model code 2020 [10] results in a lower value and this can be justified by the adoption of the parameters established by their respective equations. In summary, the parameters that were inserted in the equation determined by the fib model code 2020 [10] are, in general, related to the flexural strength of the composite (which are determined through the flexural test), which can justify the greater discrepancies found. In addition, the analysis also illustrates the conservative aspect of the equation proposed in this work for predicting the tensile stress of fibers in the tensioned part of the concrete.

It is worth noting that, although the performance of fibers in concrete is also associated with the fiber content, fiber shape factor and fiber-matrix adhesion, and these parameters vary according to the fiber used, it is clear in this work that the methodology used in the analysis of the mechanical behavior of the FRC can directly influence the analysis of the tensile stress of fibers, which, consequently, promotes variations in the dimensioning aspects of the FRC elements. In this context, it is suggested that future work compare the equation proposed in this work with other standards, such as ACI 544.8R [11], to investigate the variations found by the applied methods.

Finally, another relevant aspect to be mentioned is that this study was developed for concretes with a characteristic compressive strength less than or equal to 50 MPa, and the behavior for concretes with

higher strengths may be different from that observed. However, although this work cannot be adapted to all situations of FRC structural elements, it is clear from the investigation that there may be an influence of the methodology used to obtain the tensile stress of fibers, which shows future perspectives for new works on the subject.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

According to the investigation carried out, it is noted that from the equilibrium of the section and through the Euler-Bernoulli theory of bending in beams, an equation was defined in this work regarding the tensile stress of fibers in the tensioned part of the concrete. And to establish this parameter, for steel fiber reinforced fluid concrete beams (SFRFC) and for polymer fiber reinforced fluid concrete beams (PFRFC), situations of section reinforced with fibers and reinforcement and of section reinforced only with fibers were analyzed.

Thus, after establishing the equation, the equation was compared with the equations determined in accordance with the fib model code 2020. From the comparison, it was noticed that for the situation of section reinforced with fibers and reinforcement, the values did not present significant discrepancies, where the variations were around 12%. However, for the situation of section reinforced only with fibers, the variations were more discrepant, where the largest variations were around 31%, which illustrates the differences adopted in the methodologies used regarding the mechanical behavior of FRC beams.

In general, it is clear that the result defined from the equation established in this work results in a higher value and that established in accordance with the fib model code 2020 results in a lower value, and this can be justified by the adoption of the parameters established by their respective equations. In summary, the parameters that were inserted in the equation determined by the fib model code 2020 are, in general, related to the flexural strength of the composite and are “sensitive” to the test results, while the parameters that were inserted in the equation proposed in this work are more related to the characteristics of the materials, which may justify the greater discrepancies found.

Furthermore, the greatest variations observed were in the configurations of sections reinforced only with fibers, which was already an expected result, since in this configuration the fibers have a predominant performance in the tensile strength of the concrete and, consequently, depending on the methodology used, significantly influence the tensile stress of the FRC. Therefore, and taking into account that the equation proposed in this work can be used in the dimensioning of FRC elements, the values obtained by this methodology will represent the conservative aspect of the proposed equation.

Therefore, it can be said that the present work achieved the goals initially suggested, where an equation was established regarding the tensile stress of fibers for fiber reinforced fluid concrete beams (FRFC), in which this establishment can contribute with guidelines regarding the structural aspects of FRFC beams, as it will allow a more complete analysis of the mechanical behavior of fiber reinforced fluid concrete.

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